

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

E-ISSN 3082-4397

P-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 6

ECHOES

of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

JUNE 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20725333

Under Her Umbrella

Yes, one thing is very important when it rains suddenly. I have noticed how a sudden rain can change the mood of my students and colleagues on several afternoons, especially after classes. The weather may be fair in the morning, but late in the afternoon, the sky darkens and heavy rain starts. That's when everybody starts looking around, asking the same questions: "Do you have an umbrella?" "Where did I put mine?" "Someone took my umbrella again?"

To some people, this may seem ordinary and just part of the rainy days. But for me, it has become extraordinary. I regularly see those umbrellas left in corners suddenly become useful when the rain starts. Some are bent and old, while others are just broken pieces. Even a broken umbrella is useful when people want to go home. At that point, no one really cares about its appearance or condition. What matters is that, it can still keep someone dry in the rain. I find this amusing, particularly when someone rushed to the door to check if there was an umbrella left. Sometimes it stays in the same spot for days because no one claims it. Other times, it disappears forever. It's odd how something so useful can be easily forgotten when the sky is clear but quickly remembered when it rains.

This scene always reminds me of my grandmother. When I was a kid, I saw her gathering broken items that others had thrown away. Among them were damaged slippers and umbrellas. At first, I couldn't understand why she would bring home something that seemed useless. Later, I realized my grandmother saw value in things that most people overlooked. Behind her house, there was often a pile of objects that looked like trash. There were old slippers, empty bottles, containers, small pieces of wood, and umbrellas with broken frames. To me, as a child, it looked like clutter. I wondered why she kept all of them. I even thought maybe she collected them to sell because some people buy broken umbrellas by the kilo.

One day, I finally asked her, "La, what will you do with that umbrella? It's already broken." She looked at me and smiled. "This is not completely broken, apo," she said. "It can still be fixed." At that time, I didn't take her words seriously. To me, a broken umbrella was just that, a broken umbrella. If one part was bent or one side couldn't open properly, or if the fabric was loose, then it was useless. I hadn't yet realized that some things aren't truly useless. They just need someone patient enough to fix them. Then I understood her.

The rain was heavy that Monday morning. I was about to leave for school, but I couldn't because the rain was pouring. The road outside was wet, and every step would leave

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ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741
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my uniform soaked. I stood by the door, waiting for the rain to let up, but it showed no signs of stopping. Then my grandmother came to me and handed me an umbrella. I recognized it right away. It was the same umbrella she had picked up before, the one I thought was only good for the trash. But this time, it was no longer broken. It wasn't new or beautiful, but it was fixed. The bent part was straightened. The loose cloth was secured. The handle was old, but it was strong enough to hold. That morning, I went to school under an umbrella someone else had tossed away, and my grandmother had saved. I didn't fully realize it then, but that simple umbrella taught me a lesson I would remember for life. It showed me that usefulness doesn't disappear just because something is damaged. Sometimes, what others reject still has value when you give it care and attention.

During those years, owning things wasn't always easy. Raincoats were helpful on rainy days, but we couldn't just grab one anytime. If a family had a raincoat, it had to be taken care of properly so it would last, maybe up to a decade. The same went for umbrellas. If my mother bought an umbrella and I took it to school, I had to bring it back home. Losing it wasn't just a small mistake. It could mean scolding, punishment, or even a long walk back to school to search for it. An umbrella was not just an extra item. It was part of surviving the rainy season. It helped a child arrive at school dry. It helped a parent get to work, even when the sky looked threatening. It helped someone get home without catching a cold. It was simple, but it mattered a lot.

I remember how umbrellas used to be large and sturdy. They were hard to fit in a bag like the foldable ones we have today. You had to carry them, lean them against a wall, or leave them by the door. Yet, many of them lasted a long time. They were plain and heavy, not very stylish, but they were dependable every time. Today, umbrellas come in various designs and sizes. Some are small enough to fit in a bag. Some look fancy and expensive. But even with these changes, umbrellas are still easy to lose. Maybe it's because we only think of them when we need them. That's why many people write their names on their umbrellas, a small reminder that it belongs to someone. But even with a name, an umbrella can still go missing. Sometimes, you might see someone using an umbrella that looks just like yours, but you're hesitant to ask if it's really yours. You don't want to offend the person. So, you stay quiet and let it go.

The more I think about it, the more I realize that we don't just forget umbrellas; we forget people too. We overlook their kindness, efforts, and quiet presence in our lives. We get so used to being protected, helped, and loved that we often don't see the hands that support us. Some people are like umbrellas. They are there when life gets tough. They shield us in ways we don't always notice. They remind us what to bring, prepare what we need, fix what we break, and stick with us through everyday moments. Since they are always around, we sometimes assume they will always be there.

Then, when they leave or when they get tired, we start to see their worth. This is one of the unfortunate patterns of human life. We often appreciate things only after we lose them. We realize the value of a handkerchief only when sweat is running down our face, the value of money when it becomes hard to find, and the value of time after it has gone. Most painfully,

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we understand the importance of people when their chair is empty, their voice is missing, and their care is no longer available.

The umbrella makes me think of this. When it's not raining, it might stay in a corner, unseen and forgotten. Still, its value remains whether it's needed or not. My grandmother understood this better than I did. She knew that not everything thrown away deserves to be forgotten. Looking back, I see that my grandmother was like the umbrella she fixed. She wasn't loud about what she did. She didn't ask for praise. She just helped, fixed, saved, and protected quietly. Her love was practical. It wasn't always shown in long words. Now that I'm older, I realize that life is full of blessings that don't always look impressive. Many blessings are ordinary, old, or worn with time. Some take the form of people we see every day and often fail to appreciate. Yes, an umbrella may be simple, but it teaches an important lesson. Whenever I see umbrellas left by doors or forgotten in corners, I think of my grandmother, the umbrella she repaired, and the lesson that came with it. Under my grandmother's umbrella, I learned to see value in what others ignore and to recognize love in simple actions. Long after the rain stopped, that lesson stayed with me, and I will always treasure it.